

Title: Computational Biology/Bioinformatics on a budget.

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Abstract: Computational biology/bioinformatics is very expensive, but thanks to the recent developments in the semiconductor industry there is a relative budget solution. Here I present how a budget lab was set up based on the grant experience for *in silico* screening of compounds, which target the quorum sensing system of *P. aeruginosa*. This knowledge could be used by other lower income countries that are trying to perform computational biology/bioinformatics studies.

Keywords: Computational biology, bioinformatics, budget, virtual screening, molecular docking, molecular dynamics.

Introduction:

There are significant challenges that need to be overcome. According to World Bank the current economic situation of Armenia remains difficult and was classified until recently as lower middle income country [1], but grant amounts are still very limited and used meticulously. Computational biology/bioinformatics is very

expensive, but thanks to the recent developments in the semiconductor industry there is a relative budget solution. The recent release of the AMDs CPU (central processing units) it is possible to acquire CPUs with 8 cores and 16 threads for a reasonable price. A central processing unit (CPU) is the electronic circuitry within a computer that carries out the instructions of a computer program. Building budget computational lab has never been that easy or affordable, but now it is. This paper is based on my experience from the ANSEF research grant (molbio 4904). The purpose of the grant is the search of potential inhibitors of the quorum sensing system of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, which is one of the “ESKAPE” pathogens and it is multidrug resistant [2]. So it is essential to find a way how to counteract these bacteria. The project involves combination of molecular docking, molecular dynamics and analysis of the data using different machine learning techniques. Two computers with GTX 1070 GPUs were acquired on a budget of 2300 USD. Graphics processing units (GPUs) have emerged as an economical and powerful alternative to traditional CPUs for scientific computation. Molecular dynamics simulations can leverage GPU acceleration

Set Up of Budget Lab:

Two computers with Ryzen 1700 CPUs were acquired, each Ryzen 1700 has 8 physical cores and 16 threads. So with the 2 computers a total of 16 cores and 32 threads are available for computation. Thanks to the availability of gigabit networks it is feasible to transfer data among the computers. So for that purpose the 2 acquired computers were connected to a gigabit network via router. Router is a network device, which allows to connect two or more devices. For the gigabit router Mikrotik Hap AC² was used. This router features 4 core ARM processor and 256 megabytes of Random Access Memory (RAM), thus it can ensure full gigabit network bandwidth. On the computers Linux based operating system were installed, specifically Ubuntu 16.04. Linux operating systems are dominating in the scientific field. Newer Linux based operating systems can also be installed.

For the molecular docking a different approach was taken which involves using multiple molecular docking programs [3]. The list of the software packages includes Autodock Vina [4], LeDock [5], rDock [6] and FlexAid [7]. From the list only Autodock Vina [4] is capable of leveraging multiple cores for performing docking with a single molecule and the rest of the programs are single threaded. So obtaining samples by running in sequential mode is not effective, even detrimental.

This raises the question on how to distribute computational tasks and retrieve the results in an effective manner. For that purpose there is a library, which facilitates this whole process. The name of the library is Dask [8] and it is available for Python, which is a multipurpose programming language and has become one of the defacto languages for data science and machine learning. The best way for installing Dask [8] is through the Anaconda package manager, which is very easy to install under any operating system and can solve the issues with library dependencies. Dask works by launching the necessary clients on the computers. DASK has two types: workers and schedulers. The dask worker is launched on the computer that will perform the computations, while scheduler ensures the synchronization and information transfer. It should be noted that firewall can become an issue, because dask worker assigns random ports, but this can be fixed by making sure that dask worker uses specific ports and then setup the firewall of the system.

The only thing left is to install the docking programs on the computers and setup the script so it will launch the docking programs remotely on the worker computers. Dask facilitates the whole process, which includes running the simulations and data retrieval using the gigabit network. The schematics of the setup are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig 1. The schematic of the budget bioinformatics lab.

Concluding remarks:

Hardware has changed dramatically in recent years. Nowadays it possible to acquire desktop computers with 8 physical cores, which was reserved for workstations. Thanks to the availability of Gigabit networking devices it possible to distribute tasks such as molecular docking, and increase output as well as perform virtual screening. This approach could offer a low maintenance and programming cost strategy for lower middle income countries.

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